

You have one qubit with value 0 in **2D**.

Flip the value to 1 without using an X- or Y-gate.

Bit Flip = Solution

0
Player 1

Starting state: 0

Easy 2D 3D

Quantum operations: H1 Z H1

Winning state:

Number of measurements: 100

Undo Reset Measure

Complete end state:
 $1 \cdot \exp(i \cdot 0n) \cdot 1 \rangle$

Background: Quantum interference is one of the most important concepts in quantum computing. It is at the heart of almost all quantum enhancements, such as finding a solution to a specific problem exponentially faster than a classical computer. Two of the most popular enhanced quantum algorithms are factorizing prime numbers (Shor algorithm) and the search through a large unstructured data set (Grover algorithm).

You start with a $|\psi\rangle = |2\rangle + |1\rangle + |0\rangle$ quantum state in **3D**.
(Play an H_1 gate on a $|0\rangle$ input state to get the initial state.)

Make sure that you will win the round with 2 points by
generating the state $|2\rangle$ without playing more than three cards.
Don't use any X or Y gates.

Dream big = Solution

The screenshot shows the 'Endless Fun' quantum riddle game interface. On the left, a vertical panel shows the game state for 'Player 1' at level 0. It contains four cards: the top two are blue with a penguin and a '1' icon; the third is red with a bear and a '2' icon; the bottom one is blue with a polar bear and a '1' icon. The main game area has a black background with the title 'Endless Fun' in colorful text. It includes a 'Starting state' input field with '0', difficulty buttons for 'Easy', '2D', and '3D' (the '3D' button is highlighted), and a 'Quantum operations' list containing 'H1', 'H1', 'Z1', and 'H3'. A grid of quantum gates is available, including 'I', 'X1', 'X2', 'Y1', 'Y2', 'Z1', 'Z2', 'H1', 'H2', 'H3', 'CX1', 'CXr', 'SWAP1', 'SWAPr', and 'Cancel'. The 'Winning state' input field is empty. The 'Number of measurements' is set to '100'. At the bottom, there are 'Undo', 'Reset', and 'Measure' buttons. The 'Complete end state' is displayed as $1 \cdot \exp(i\pi/2n) |2\rangle$.

Note to the solution: Interference with qudits requires an additional Hadamard gate in contrast to the 2D case (see “Bit-Flip” riddle).

Background: Although the field of high-dimensional quantum information is still in its infancy, it is a promising candidate for future quantum computers. It is already known, e.g., that qudits can simplify some quantum computational tasks as they require less multi-qudit operations.

You have two arbitrary qubits in **2D**.

Swap the two qubit values whatever their input is.

You can't use a SWAP-gate.

Let's Swap - Solution

The image shows a diagram of a Swap gate and a quantum circuit simulator interface. The diagram on the left illustrates a Swap gate with two qubits, labeled '1 Player 1' and '0 Player 2'. Each qubit is represented by a card with a tiger face, a 'Control' label, and a 'Target' label. The simulator interface on the right is titled 'Endless Fun' and features a starting state of 10, a difficulty level of 2D, and a number of measurements of 100. The quantum operations list includes CXr, CXl, CXr, SWAPl, SWAPr, and Cancel. The complete end state is displayed as $1 \cdot \exp(i\pi) |01\rangle$.

Background: All quantum computational tasks can be performed using only basic quantum logic gates, which are called elementary quantum gates. By cleverly arranging them, it is possible to perform complex operations and large-scale computational tasks. Building a SWAP gate out of CX gates is a simple example of it.

You start with a $|000\rangle$ quantum state in **3D**.

Play quantum operations so that there is only one unpredictable winner each round.

Well-Balanced Odds - Solution

Background: Entanglement can not only be realized between two qubits, but also between several qudits. Entangled states between many quantum systems are an integral part in quantum computing and are jointly responsible for the quantum-computational speed-up. They are also very fragile: one broken qudit destroys the entanglement between all.

Start with the state $|00\rangle$ in **2D**.

Generate a quantum state with only one unpredictable winner. This condition should still hold if you play H_1 or H_2 gates on both states at the same time.

Jingle Bells - Solution

Background: The generated state is the anti-symmetric $|\Psi^-\rangle$ Bell state. Like all Bell-states, $|\Psi^-\rangle$ is maximally entangled, i.e. the local outcome is entirely random while the global outcome is perfectly correlated. $|\Psi^-\rangle$ is the only state that always gives anti-correlated outcomes independent of the measurement direction. H-gates change the measurement direction and toggle all other Bell states between correlated and anti-correlated states.

You start with a $|000\rangle$ quantum state in **3D**.

Create a state in which the first and last qudit are entangled in three dimensions. The qudit in the middle should be uncorrelated.

Hint: Generate a maximally entangled state (such as a GHZ state) first. Then disentangle the second qudit.

The Third Wheel - Solution

0 0 0
Player 1 Player 2 Player 3

Starting state: 000 Easy 2D 3D

Quantum operations:
H1 I1
CXr CXr CXI
I1 CXI

Winning state:

Number of measurements: 100

Undo Reset Measure

Complete end state:
 $1/\sqrt{3} \cdot \exp(i \cdot 2/3\pi) \cdot |202\rangle + 1/\sqrt{3} \cdot \exp(i \cdot 2/3\pi) \cdot |101\rangle + 1/\sqrt{3} \cdot \exp(i \cdot 0\pi) \cdot |000\rangle$

Note to the solution: The second qudit can only have one value ($|0\rangle$), hence it is separable from the other two qudits, which remain entangled.

Background: The architecture of quantum computers does not always allow operations on distant qudits. Therefore, it is important to have the possibility to generate links, such as entanglement here, between distant nodes even if they can't directly interact with each other.